

NOTES

Studies on Niobium(v) Complex with 1-Phenyl-3-methyl-4-(2-methoxybenzeneazo)- 5-pyrazolone

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PYRAZOLONE ring, due to its reactive 4-position, undergoes coupling reaction with a number of aryldiazonium chlorides to form 4-aryazo derivatives. These azo dyes are good chelating agents having azo group *ortho* to OH group and usually form five-membered ring with metal atoms. Many metal complexes of these azo dyes have been reported¹. The present communication reports the complexation of niobium(v) with 1-phenyl-3-methyl-4-(2-methoxybenzeneazo)-5-pyrazolone (PMMBP).

Experimental

Pure NbCl₅ (Fluka), A.R. grade chemicals and freshly distilled DMF were used. Nb^v was estimated in the solution by precipitating with tannin and weighing as niobium pentoxide. The reagent (PMMBP) was prepared by literature method^{2,3} and recrystallised from hot dioxane to orange crystals, m.p. 165°.

Niobium pentachloride and PMMBP were separately dissolved in DMF, then mixed in 1 : 2 molar ratio and refluxed for ~2 h. The complex separated as light brown precipitate, was washed several times with DMF and finally with ethanol. The complex did not show any sharp melting point but decomposed above 250°. The complex is sparingly soluble in DMSO and benzene (Found : C, 54.1 ; H, 4.2 ; N, 14.2 ; Cl, 4.6 ; Nb, 13.1. Nb C_{8.4}H_{9.0}N₈O₅Cl calcd. for : C, 53.7 ; H, 3.9 ; N, 14.7 ; Cl, 4.6 ; Nb, 12.2%).

Ir spectra (4 000–200 cm⁻¹) were recorded in nujol on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurements were made on Gouy balance using Hg[Co(CNS)₄] as the calibrant. Diamagnetic corrections for ligand molecule were made using Pascal's constants⁴.

Results and Discussion

Ir spectra of the ligand showed significant changes after complexation with the metal. A broad band in the region 3 320–3 280 cm⁻¹ (OH) was absent in the spectra of the complex. Sharp

peak at 1 540 cm⁻¹ (C=O) in the spectra of ligand was absent in the spectra of the complex suggesting complexation involving enolic form of the ligand. Two bands present in the ligand spectra at 1 110 and 1 210 cm⁻¹ were assigned to C—O stretching and O—H bending vibrations. The band due to OH bending was absent in the spectra of the complex and that due to ν_{C—O} shifted to 1 160 cm⁻¹ indicating coordination through enolic OH group^{5,6}. Azo group frequency shifted from 1 600 to 1 550 cm⁻¹, suggesting coordination through nitrogen of the azo group. Other bands observed in ligand spectra were unaffected in the spectra of the complex indicating that they are not involved in coordination. A band at 940 cm⁻¹ in spectra of the complex was assigned to ν_{Nb—O}⁷. The 575 cm⁻¹ band was assigned to ν_{Nb—O} which was in agreement with the Nb—O stretching vibrations in niobium alkoxides^{8,9}. The terminal Nb—Cl stretching frequency was observed at 330 cm⁻¹ (Ref. 10). The effective magnetic moment of the complex (0.5 B.M.) may be due to temperature-independent paramagnetism.

On the basis of the above studies the following possible structure is proposed for the complex.

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Palladium(II) Chloride Complexes of some Aryl Methyl Sulphides. Part-2. Substituent Effect on Pd—S and Pd—Cl Stretching Frequencies

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LOW frequency infrared spectra of the palladium(II) complexes of methyl phenyl sulphide as ligand have been recorded¹⁻³ and the stretching frequencies for Pd—S and Pd—Cl are assigned to be 294 and 370 cm⁻¹, respectively. The other intense band at 342 cm⁻¹ has been attributed³ to the asymmetric stretch for Pd—Cl. These spectral observations are in agreement with the assumption that the complex is trans-square-planar. Such square-planar complexes have been the subject of previous infrared investigations^{4,5}. In trans-complexes of palladium(II) only one metal-chlorine vibration would be ir-active and $\nu_{\text{Pd-Cl}}$ stretch in the range 353–359 cm⁻¹ was noticed. In the present study, the infrared spectra of palladium(II) chloride complexes of several mono-, di-, and tri-substituted-phenyl methyl sulphides have been prepared⁶ and recorded in the region 900–200 cm⁻¹ and the $\nu_{\text{Pd-Cl}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Pd-S}}$ stretching frequencies are assigned. The substituent effects over $\nu_{\text{Pd-S}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Pd-Cl}}$ have been discussed.

Results and Discussion

The spectral assignments (Table 1) reveal that the complexes have trans-configuration (D_{2h} symmetry) and the data are in close agreement with those reported earlier^{1-3,7}. For the complex trans-PdCl₂(C₆H₅SCH₃)₂, two strong bands at 373 (asym) and 342 cm⁻¹ (sym) (the former being more intense than the latter) for Pd—Cl and a medium band at 298 cm⁻¹ for Pd—S are obtained. When the OCH₃ group is at *para*-position, the resonance effect outweighs the inductive effect which has a net electron-releasing tendency to the benzene ring, and so the Pd—S stretching frequency is decreased to a lower region (277 cm⁻¹) than that of the parent

compound. The OCH₃ in *meta*-position being an electron-withdrawing group, increased the Pd—S stretching frequency to a higher region as expected. The electron withdrawing NO₂ group at *para*-position attracts electrons through conjugative interaction and so the trans-PdCl₂(*p*-NO₂C₆H₄-SCH₃) complex has its Pd—S stretching frequency at higher region (326 cm⁻¹) than its parent compound. Similarly, NO₂ in *meta*-position also acts as electron-withdrawing group. The halogen atoms in *para*-position are acting as electron-releasing group. This is obviously due to the presence of SCH₃ group in the *para*-position. Here sulphur is an electron acceptor and there is a possibility of the expansion of its valence shell. On the other hand, halogen atoms in *meta*-position acts as electron-withdrawing groups through inductive effect alone. The shift of OH band to the lower region (upto 40 cm⁻¹) in the complexes of hydroxy and carboxylic substituted phenyl methyl sulphides shows the presence of intramolecular hydrogen bonding between OH and chlorine. The carbonyl frequency of *meta* and *para* carboxylic groups in their complexes gets increased when compared with the ligands. But in the case of *ortho*-isomer it is almost the same. This may be attributed to higher stability of the complexes having *meta* and *para* carboxylic substituted phenyl methyl sulphides when compared to the *ortho* isomer.

The behaviour of methoxy in the *ortho*-position is unexpected from the consideration of steric and increased inductive effects. In this case, the free rotation of methoxy group is restricted and increases its probability of attaining planarity with the benzene ring. Thus there can be enhanced resonance of methoxy group which outweighs its inductive effect. This may be the cause for steric enhancement of resonance and with the result the Pd—S stretching frequency decreases to 281 cm⁻¹. The frequency increase (319 cm⁻¹) in the complex dichlorobis(2,6-dimethylphenyl methyl sulphide)-palladium(II) is due to steric inhibition of resonance, as expected. The results of Pd—S stretching frequencies in complexes of *ortho*-substituted ligands show that the electronic effects as well as steric effects are operating. A strong σ -electron donor exerts a weakening effect on the M—S bond, and π -acceptor ligand removes the electron density from the metal⁸. It is generally found that all these substituted phenyl methyl sulphides are good trans-directing ligands. Some π -bonding between palladium and sulphur is also responsible for the trans-directing property of the ligands. Pure palladium(II) chloride exhibits Pd—Cl stretch at 337 cm⁻¹ as a strong band. This frequency moves to higher region in all the complexes. A perusal of the Pd—Cl frequencies of the complexes (Table 1) clearly shows that the Pd—Cl bonds are stronger in the complexes of *para*-substituted phenyl methyl sulphides. The Pd—Cl strength in these complexes is in the order, *para* > *ortho* > *meta*. In aromatic

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